

The first steps of carpology in Kosova: the example of Ulpiana's Roman town

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Abstract

In anticipation of the Mission Archéologique Européenne au Kosova (MAEKO) program, the study and promotion of the archaeological heritage of Ulpiana (Kosova), an archaeobotanical study – specifically a particular carpological analysis - has been underway since 2018. This study is directly linked to the archaeological excavations of sectors 1300 /1300, 1300/1500 and 1400/1400. Although still modest, this study holds undeniable scientific significance, as it represents the first of its kind conducted in Ulpiana, and more widely in Kosova and on the territory of ancient Dardania. The carpological data presented here are therefore new and exceptional, because they inaugurate research into food consumption in this chrono-cultural region. The excavation of sectors 1300/1300, 1300/1500 and 1400/1400, led by Milot Berisha (IAK), Christophe Goddard (CNRS-PSL) and Arben Hajdari (University of Prishtina), uncovered structures from the Roman period and Byzantine periods. Anthropogenic levels revealed, including functional stratigraphic units or carbonized deposits, were the subject of spot sampling of sediments. This protocol was implemented by Florian Jedrusiak (SDAVO-UMR7041-Equipe GAMMA) in consultation with Christophe Goddard and Vincent Bernollin (CNRS-PSL, AOROC). This analysis aims to improve the overall understanding of the Ulpiana site, particularly with regard to its plant economy. It is mainly a question of determining which plant foodstuffs were consumed by the populations who occupied the town between the 1st and 6th centuries AD.

Keywords: *carpology, Ulpiana, plant economy, Kosova, Dardania*

What is carpology and what is it for?

Carpology is the study of seeds and fruits found in archaeological contexts. Seeds can be preserved through carbonization (exposure to fire), imbibition (in environments with very high humidity), or mineralization (primarily in latrines or contexts with high limestone concentrations). All archaeological contexts have the potential to yield seeds. To study these seeds, a 10-liter sample of raw sediment is collected. The sediment

is then sieved using a column with a 0.3 mm mesh and subsequently sorted under a stereomicroscope at magnifications ranging from $\times 8$ to $\times 50$. The first European research in this field dates to the 19th century and was conducted by the Swiss paleobotanist O. Heer, who systematically studied plant remains collected in various prehistoric lakeside villages (Renfrew 1991). However, it was not until the second half of the 20th century that the discipline experienced significant growth. Early studies focused on plants cultivated and consumed during recent prehistoric periods, with a particular emphasis on the origins of agriculture in the Near East and its diffusion to Europe. One of the key objectives was to identify and date the domestication of cultivated plants, with cereals and legumes receiving the most attention (Bouby 2000).

A synthesis of research for Europe and Southwest Asia was published in the 2000s by D. Zohary and M. Hopf (Zohary and Hopf 1994). In France, significant research began in the 1970s, spearheaded by J. Erroux. These efforts traced the evolution of cultivated and gathered plant species from the Mesolithic to the modern era (Ruas and Marinval 1991).

Advancements in scientific techniques, methodological improvements in plant identification, and the development of reliable sampling methods at archaeological sites have facilitated new research avenues over the past four decades. Today, carpology provides increasingly precise information about the plants that shaped the environment and resources of past societies. The enrichment of the discipline, including new taxonomic identifications and expanded documentary evidence, has significantly advanced the field (Bouby 2000).

The carpological approach has become increasingly complex over the past four decades. It no longer provides simple lists of plants but aims to identify the stages of agricultural practices, from land preparation to consumption, including the processing, storage, and potential trade of harvests. Consequently, carpologists are no longer solely focused on cultivated plant seeds. Other plant remains related to these cultivated taxa, such as various parts of cereal ears (husks, rachises, spikelets), are playing an increasingly significant role (Bouby 2000). Additionally, weed seeds that colonize crops (agricultural weeds) are of particular interest for interpreting archaeological sites (Bouby 2000).

The development of carpology has led to two complementary approaches. The first, described as “ecological,” seeks to understand the ecological properties of contemporary plant species to draw conclusions about past environments. The second approach is considered more “technical” and involves examining specific anthropogenic marks on plant remains within a sample to highlight particular agricultural practices. These approaches are not mutually exclusive; rather, a comprehensive carpological study should integrate both methods (Bouby 2000).

As the discipline evolved, carpologists began distinguishing between two main types of carpological assemblages. The first type, paleobiocenosis, refers to assemblages artificially gathered in a specific context, such as a silo or granary. These assemblages are significant because they result from a single human action, such as storing a harvest. Consequently, the ecological or technical convergence of the components of the archaeological context is highly meaningful (Bouby 2000). Paleobiocenosis overlaps with the concept of a “closed ensemble” (Marinval 1989), meaning that the studied

remains were deposited at one time in a structure and originate from plants—whether cultivated or weeds—that grew in the same habitat (Bouby 2000). A typical example of paleobiocenosis is a storage site containing the remains of burned crops, including cultivated plants and weeds from the same fields (Bouby 2000).

The second type of assemblage, known as thanatocenosis, involves seeds of diverse origins without a functional link between them (Behre and Jacomet 1991; Willerding 1971). A good example is landfill samples, where waste accumulates over time without intentional organization (Bouby 2000).

Interpreting carpological contexts becomes more challenging when dealing with thanatocenoses (Behre and Jacomet 1991; Willerding 1971). It is essential to differentiate between these two types of assemblages and, when possible, combine them in studies. Both types provide valuable insights for reconstructing rural landscapes and agrarian practices, but they differ in relevance and interpretative complexity (Bouby 2000).

2. Method

2.1 Site

The archaeological site of Ulpiana is located in the municipality of Gračanica, eight kilometers southeast of Prishtina. The site is an ancient Roman settlement that spans over thirty-five hectares of agricultural plains, situated at the foot of a hill system that borders it to the south and along the Sitnica River, which flows approximately three hundred meters north of its walls. The city was established at the crossroads of two major routes: one road connected the Dalmatian coast, north of Dyrrachium, to the Danubian limes and Dacia; the other route provided access to Thessaloniki via Stobi in Macedonia. Ulpiana's Roman foundation was closely tied to the conquest of Dacia, for which the province of Moesia Superior, to which the city belonged, served as a strategic rear base. Ulpiana was a critical stop on journeys between the East and West but faced significant challenges during the barbarian incursions of the 5th, 6th, and 7th centuries AD.¹

2.2 Study context

Structures with a high potential for carporest conservation, such as charcoal layers and the Cloaca Maxima, were specifically selected for sampling. In other cases, such as post holes, selections were made with the aim of refining the understanding of certain contexts. The dating of these structures was facilitated through ceramic analysis and stratigraphic reasoning.

The carpological study was not systematic, meaning not all excavated structures were analyzed. Given its focus on a restricted area, this research provides only a partial view of the site. Nevertheless, its value remains significant, particularly because it establishes a solid foundation for understanding the plant economy of the ancient populations that occupied the site of Ulpiana and, more broadly, the region of Dardania. Since 2018, 60 samples representing 54 stratigraphic units have been studied. In total,

Date	1st century AD	2nd century CE	2nd and 3rd centuries CE	3rd and 4th centuries AD	4th centuries AD	4th and 5th centuries AD	5th centuries AD	5th and 6th centuries AD	6th centuries AD	Roman period	indefinite period
number of samples	1	4	11	7	5	2	3	1	6	2	17
Volume (l)	3	27	45	10	44	12	56	8	48	3.4	35.2
Conservation	carbonization	carbonization	carbonization	carbonization	carbonization	carbonization	carbonization	carbonization	carbonization	carbonization	carbonization

Sample number	50	48	40	55	47	49	50	51	52
US	757	751	610	745	741	715			
Context	Anthropic charcoal layer	Ceramic							
Sector	1405/1408								
Volume (l)	3	7	10	6	6	2	2	1	1
Densityl	1,7	3,4	0	2,4	4,4	1	0	1	4
Date	1st century AD	2nd century CE			2nd and 3rd centuries CE				

Sample number	53	54	55	25	27	28	29	30	31
US	727		731	301	302	303	354	355	365
Context	Anthropic charcoal layer	Anthropic charcoal layer	Anthropic charcoal layer	Coal layer	Exterior of the potter's kiln	Potter's kiln	Coal layer	Coal Layer	Potter's kiln
Sector	1405/1407			1300/1500					
Volume (l)	2	2	5	6	6	6	5	5	6
Densityl	2	1	5,8	0	5,8	0,4	0,8	0	8,6
Date	2nd and 3rd centuries CE								

Sample number	35	9	10	35	41	11	7	46	6
US	550	298	299	592	512	402	299	58E	281
Context	Anthropic charcoal layer	Clava / Maxima	Anthropic charcoal layer	Anthropic charcoal layer	Anthropic charcoal layer				
Sector	1100/1300								
Volume (l)	10	8	8	10	8	10	5	7	5
Densityl	0,2	1,5	0,5	0,2	0	1,2	0	1,4	0,2
Date	3rd and 4th centuries AD	6th centuries AD				4th and 5th centuries AD		6th centuries AD	

Sample number	42	43	44	56	57	58	37	34	45
US	613	617		572	574	705	588	514	192
Context	Anthropic charcoal layer								
Sector	1300/1300			1300/1500			1300/1300		
Volume (l)	9	18	8	15	1	7	98	8	10
Densityl	1,2	1	2,63	2	1	1,5	10,0	0	0,8
Date	6th centuries AD						5th and 6th centuries AD		6th centuries AD

Sample number	32	33	2	3	4	1	17	5	8
US	453		156	200	205	190	405	280	294
Context	Ditch	Ditch	Anthropic charcoal layer	Anthropic charcoal layer	Anthropic charcoal layer	Anthropic charcoal layer	Clava / Maxima	Anthropic charcoal layer	Anthropic charcoal layer
Sector	1300/1300								
Volume (l)	5	8	10	10	5	10	98	5	6
Densityl	4,4	5,5	8,4	1,1	1,2	0,8	2,6	1,6	0,2
Date	6th centuries AD				Roman period		indefinite period		

Sample number	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21
US	237-238	235-240	215-220	221-222	227-229	223-224	225-226	235-236	231-232
Context	post hole	post hole	post hole	post hole	post hole	post hole	post hole	post hole	post hole
Sector	1100/1300								
Volume (l)	1,6	0,5	1	1	0,2	1	0,3	2	0,8
Densityl	0,67	0	29	1	30	0	0	6,5	0
Date	indefinite period								

Sample number	22	23	24	25	35	38
US	225-230	234-235	241-242	251-252	567	587
Context	post hole	post hole	post hole	post hole	Anthropic charcoal layer	Anthropic charcoal layer
Sector	1100/1300					
Volume (l)	3	0,4	2	0,5	6	6
Densityl	2	5	3	0	0,33	2,4
Date	indefinite period					

Figure 1: List of Ulpiana samples

2.3. Sample processing

2.3.1. Sieving

All 60 sediment samples were processed using a sieving method. The samples were completely sieved with water using a sieve column with mesh sizes of 4 mm, 2 mm, 1

mm, and 315 μm . The mesh size was chosen based on the diversity of the paleo-seeds being analyzed: while some seeds measure in centimeters, the vast majority are only a few millimeters in size (Buxó 1992). This technique allows for the recovery of all seeds, even the smallest ones, such as those from wild plants.

A gentle water jet, combined with a soft brush, was used to dissolve the sediment and release the plant macroremains without crushing them on the sieve grid. The material remaining on the sieve was then placed on plates to dry (Marinval 1999). Additionally, floating particles collected during sieving were retained for further study.

2.3.2. Sorting

The archaeobotanical remains recovered from each sieve were sorted using a stereomicroscope with magnifications ranging from $\times 8$ to $\times 60$. Each sample was fully sorted without employing sub-sampling techniques, which are sometimes used in other studies (Veen and Fieller 1982; Jones 1991; Matteredne 2001). This approach ensures a more accurate assessment of the representativeness of taxa within a sample. The use of sub-sampling would have rendered it impossible to compare data across the various sieves of the same sample (Rovira 2012).

2.3.3. The determination

The determination was made possible through the use of reference atlases (Cappers, Bekker, and Jans 2012; Cappers and Neef 2012; Cappers, Neef, and Bekker 2009; Neef, Cappers, and Bekker 2012; Beijerink 1976; Jacquat 1988; and Schotch et al. 1988) and a seed reference collection (carpothèque). The identification of seeds is based on the principle of comparative anatomy. The morphological characteristics of the seeds are compared to those of modern plants using two indices: the morphology of the complete individual and the metric indices (L = length; l = width; $\acute{e}$ = thickness) (Buxó 1992). This comparison allows each paleo-seed to be matched to a specific plant species.

Seed counts were conducted on an individual basis. Whole specimens, as well as fragments with identifiable and unique morphological characteristics, were considered individuals (often, a preserved carporect retains more than half of its original morphology) (Rovira 2012). Although the numerical data presented in the carpological tables reflect the minimum number of individuals (NMI), the fragmentation of seeds makes this estimate problematic for two main reasons. First, the number of plant components is not always standard and can vary within the same species (Jones 1991). Second, the fragmentation rate can differ significantly depending on whether it is voluntary (anthropogenic, such as during craft activities) or involuntary (due to burial processes or excavation) (Rovira 2012).

To account for these challenges, fragments of the same taxon were grouped into sets of four to be considered one complete individual (Rovira 2012). While this approach does not resolve the fundamental issue, it helps limit potential biases in interpretations. Seeds with similar characteristics were grouped under the same taxon to ensure homogenization and systematization of results. B. Pradat addressed the challenges of seed counting in a 2015 publication, specifying that all methods used to calculate the

Ulpiana (Kosovo)		Sample number				Total volume (l)		phyto-sociological code (according to Ellenberg et al. 1991)
		48	40	59	47			
US		751	610	748	741			
sector		1400/1400						
Volume (l)		7	10	5	5			27
Density!		3,4	0	2,4	4,4			
Dating		2nd century CE						
Vernacular names		Type of reste		Method of conservation				
Lambinon et alii (2012)								
Cereal								
<i>Triticum cf. spelta</i>		caryopsis		C		2		X
<i>Triticum aestivum/durum/turgidum</i>		caryopsis		C		1		X
<i>Hordeum vulgare</i>		caryopsis		C		1		X
Cerealia		caryopsis		C		2		X
Carbonized Organic Matter		COM		C		4		X
9						22		
Legume								
<i>Vicia ervilia</i>		cotyledon		C		2		X
<i>Vicia sp.</i>		cotyledon		C		1		X
<i>Pisum sativum</i>		cotyledon		C		1		X
<i>Leguminosae sativae indeterminata</i>		cotyledon		C		4		X
Messicoles and other vegetation								
3. Anthropogenic vegetation								
3.5. Artemisiete a								
<i>Galium aparine</i> agg.		seed		C		4		3.5
Other								
Fabaceae		cotyledon		C		2		X
3								

Number of reste s	24	0	12	22	58
Nombre of taxa	11	0	4	1	11
Main conservation within the structure	C	C	C	C	Carbonization

Figure 3: Carpological data for the 2nd century CE

Upliana (Kosovo) "1300/1300" RO: A Hajdari et C. Goddard	Sample number		35	9	10	39	41	11
	US		550	298	299	592	612	402
sector	1300/1300							
Volume (l)	54							
Density(l)	10	8	8	10	8	10	8	10
Dating	4th centuries AD							
Vernacular names		Type of reste	Method of conservation					
Lambinon et alii (2012)								
Cereal								
Triticum sp.	Wheat	caryopsis	C		2			X
Hordeum vulgare	Barley	caryopsis	C	1				X
Panicum miliaceum	Proso millet	caryopsis	C		1			X
Cerealia	Cerealia	caryopsis	C		1	1		X
Legume								
Lens culinaris	Lentil	cotyledon	C		1			X
Fruit								
Prunus spp.	Prunus spp.	endocarp	C		1			X
Mosses and other vegetation								
3. Anthropogenic vegetation								
Chenopodium sp.	Goosefoots	akene	C				2	3.
3.2. Blade mites								
Paspalum hydropiper	Water pepper	akene	C	1				3.211
3.3. Chenopodieta								
Chenopodium hybridum	Megle-leaved goosefoot	akene	C		7	1		9
3.5. Artemisieta								
Galium aparine agg.	Cleavers	seed	C					1
Sambucus ebulus	Danewort	seed	C			1		1
Other								
Sambucus sp.	Sambucus	seed	C		1			1
Indeterminata, carbonized								
Undetermined				1				1

Number of restes	2	12	4	2	0	12	32
Nombre of taxa	2	6	3	2	0	3	12
Main conservation within the structure	C	C	C	C	C	C	Carbonization

Figure 5: Carpological data for the 3rd and 4th centuries AD

Ulpiana (Kosovo)		Sample number										Total volume (l)	phyto-sociological code (according to Ellenberg et al. 1991)	
"1300/1500"		7	46	6	42	43	44	56	57	58	37			
"1300/1300"		US		289	688	281	613	617	672	674	700	568	77	
"1400/1400"		sector		1300/1300	1400/1400	1300/1300			1300/1500		1300/1300			
RO: A Hajdari et C. Goddard		Volume (l)		5	7	5	9	10	8	15	1	7	10	Number of restes
		Density/l		0	1,4	0,2	1,2	1	2,03	2	1	1,5	10,9	
Scientific names		Vernacular names		Type of reste		Method of conservation		4th and 5th centuries AD						
Lambinon et alii (2012)		Lambinon et alii (2012)						5th centuries AD						
Cereal														
<i>Triticum cf. spelta</i>	Spelt	caryopsis	C		1				5				6	x
<i>Triticum aestivum/durum/furgitum</i>	Common wheat	caryopsis	C		1			1			1		3	x
<i>Triticum sp.</i>	Wheat	caryopsis	C					2	7		2	1	12	x
<i>Hordeum vulgare</i>	Barley	caryopsis	C					2					2	x
<i>Secale cereale</i>	Rye	caryopsis	C				2						2	x
<i>Panicum milaceum</i>	Proso millet	caryopsis	C									1	1	x
Cereals	Cereal	caryopsis	C		3		3	3	11		1	2	23	x
Carbonized Organic Matter	Carbonized Organic Matter	COM	C						3				3	x
Legume														
<i>Vicia sp.</i>	Vetches	cotyledon	C				1	3			1		5	x
<i>Pisum sativum</i>	Pea	cotyledon	C				1						1	x
<i>Lathyrus sativus</i>	Indian pea	cotyledon	C					2					2	x
Fruit														
<i>Vitis vinifera ssp. vinifera</i>	Common grape vine	seed	C					1					1	x
<i>Juglans regia</i>	English walnut	pericarp	C				1						1	x
<i>Rubus cf. idaeus</i>	Red raspberry	akene	C					1					1	x
Mesocotels and other vegetation														
3. Anthropogenic vegetation														
<i>Chenopodium sp.</i>	Goosefoots	akene	C				1					6	7	3.
3.2. Bidentetea														
<i>Persicaria hydropiper</i>	Water pepper	akene	C									36	36	3.211
3.3 Chenopodietea														
<i>Chenopodium hybridum</i>	Mistle-leaved goosefoot	akene	C				5					10	15	3.3
<i>Sonchus asper</i>	Spiny sowthistle	seed	C				1						1	3.31
3.4. Secalietea														
<i>Fallopia convolvulus</i>	Black Bindweed	akene	C									1	1	3.4
<i>Vicia cf. tetrasperma</i>	Smooth tare	cotyledon	C					1	3				4	3.421
3.5. Artemisietea														
<i>Galium aparine</i> agg.	Cleavers	seed	C				1	1					2	3.5
3.7. Plantaginetea														
<i>Polygonum aviculare</i> agg.	Prostrate knotweed	akene	C									17	17	3.711
Other														
<i>Carex</i> sp.	Carex	akene	C			1	1		1				3	x
<i>Sambucus</i> sp.	Sambucus	seed	C				1						1	x
<i>Chenopodium</i> sp.	Goosefoots	akene	C						1				1	x
Polygonaceae	Polygonaceae	akene	C									35	35	x
Fabaceae	Legume	cotyledon	C				1						1	x
Poaceae	Grasses	caryopsis	C				1	1					2	x
Indeterminata, carbonized														
Undetermined								3		1			4	
Number of restes				0	5	1	11	10	21	30	1	5	108	193
Nombre of taxa				0	3	1	7	7	12	5	1	4	9	27
Main conservation within the structure					C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	Carbonization

Figure 6: Carpological data for the 4th and 5th centuries AD

Ulpiana (Kosovo)		Sample number							Total volume (l)	phyto-sociological code (according to Ellenberg et al. 1991)	
"1300/1306"		34	45	32	33	2	3	4			
RO: A. Hajdari et C. Goddard		US	514	192	463	195	200	209	56		
Scientific names		sector									
Lambinon et alii (2012)		1300/1300									
Vernacular names		Volume (l)									
Type of rests		Density/l									
Method of conservation		Dating									
		5th and 6th centuries AD									
		6th centuries AD									
		Number of rests									
Cereal											
<i>Triticum aestivum/durum/turgidum</i>	Common wheat	caryopsis	C			3	1			4	x
<i>Triticum cf. spelta</i>	Spelt	caryopsis	C	1						1	x
<i>Triticum sp.</i>	Wheat	caryopsis	C			5	1			6	x
<i>Hordeum vulgare</i>	Barley	caryopsis	C		2	2			2	6	x
<i>Panicum milaceum</i>	Proso millet	caryopsis	C	1						1	x
Carbonized Organic Matter	Carbonized Organic Matter	COM	C	1	2	3				6	x
Legume											
<i>Pisum sativum</i>	Pea	cotyledon	C	1		1				2	x
<i>Viola sp.</i>	Vetches	cotyledon	C			1	1			2	x
Restioids and other vegetation											
3. Anthropogenic vegetation											
<i>Chenopodium sp.</i>	Goosefoots	akene seed	C	1	6	5	15	1		28	3.
<i>Veronica hederifolia</i> agg.	ivy-leaved speedwell	seed	C				2			2	3.
3.3 Chenopodietea											
<i>Chenopodium hybridum</i>	Maple-leaved goosefoot	akene	C		2	3	58	2	1	66	3.3
<i>Chenopodium album</i> agg.	White goosefoot	akene	C					2		2	3.3
<i>Fumaria officinale</i>	Common fumitory	seed	C					1		1	3.311
3.4. Scabietea											
<i>Fallopia convolvulus</i>	Black Bindweed	akene	C	1						1	3.4
<i>Viola cf. luteoasperma</i>	Smooth tare	cotyledon	C				1			1	3.42f
3.5. Artemisietea											
<i>Galium aparine</i> agg.	Cleavers	seed	C	1				1	1	3	3.5
<i>Sambucus ebulus</i>	Danewort	seed	C			1		1		2	3.53f
3.7. Plantaginea											
<i>Polygonum aviculare</i> agg.	Prostrate knotweed	akene	C	1						1	3.711
Other											
<i>Sambucus sp.</i>	Sambucus	seed	C			1		1		2	x
<i>Carex sp.</i>	Carex	akene	C					1		1	x
<i>Lolium sp.</i>	Lolium	caryopsis	C						1	1	x
Polygonaceae	Polygonaceae	akene	C		5	16				21	x
Poaceae	Grasses	caryopsis	C		2	2		1		5	x
Indeterminata, carbonized		Undetermined			3	1	5		1	10	
Number of rests				0	8	22	44	84	11	6	175
Nombre of taxa				0	8	7	13	8	8	5	24
Main conservation within the structure					C	C	C	C	C	C	Carbonization

Figure 7: Carpological data for the 5th and 6th centuries AD

Upljana (Kosovo)	Sample number		1300/1300												Total volume [l]	phyto-sociological code (according to Ellenberg et al. 1991)																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																																							
	US	US	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12			13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	60	61	62	63	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	71	72	73	74	75	76	77	78	79	80	81	82	83	84	85	86	87	88	89	90	91	92	93	94	95	96	97	98	99	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108	109	110	111	112	113	114	115	116	117	118	119	120	121	122	123	124	125	126	127	128	129	130	131	132	133	134	135	136	137	138	139	140	141	142	143	144	145	146	147	148	149	150	151	152	153	154	155	156	157	158	159	160	161	162	163	164	165	166	167	168	169	170	171	172	173	174	175	176	177	178	179	180	181	182	183	184	185	186	187	188	189	190	191	192	193	194	195	196	197	198	199	200	201	202	203	204	205	206	207	208	209	210	211	212	213	214	215	216	217	218	219	220	221	222	223	224	225	226	227	228	229	230	231	232	233	234	235	236	237	238	239	240	241	242	243	244	245	246	247	248	249	250	251	252	253	254	255	256	257	258	259	260	261	262	263	264	265	266	267	268	269	270	271	272	273	274	275	276	277	278	279	280	281	282	283	284	285	286	287	288	289	290	291	292	293	294	295	296	297	298	299	300	301	302	303	304	305	306	307	308	309	310	311	312	313	314	315	316	317	318	319	320	321	322	323	324	325	326	327	328	329	330	331	332	333	334	335	336	337	338	339	340	341	342	343	344	345	346	347	348	349	350	351	352	353	354	355	356	357	358	359	360	361	362	363	364	365	366	367	368	369	370	371	372	373	374	375	376	377	378	379	380	381	382	383	384	385	386	387	388	389	390	391	392	393	394	395	396	397	398	399	400	401	402	403	404	405	406	407	408	409	410	411	412	413	414	415	416	417	418	419	420	421	422	423	424	425	426	427	428	429	430	431	432	433	434	435	436	437	438	439	440	441	442	443	444	445	446	447	448	449	450	451	452	453	454	455	456	457	458	459	460	461	462	463	464	465	466	467	468	469	470	471	472	473	474	475	476	477	478	479	480	481	482	483	484	485	486	487	488	489	490	491	492	493	494	495	496	497	498	499	500	501	502	503	504	505	506	507	508	509	510	511	512	513	514	515	516	517	518	519	520	521	522	523	524	525	526	527	528	529	530	531	532	533	534	535	536	537	538	539	540	541	542	543	544	545	546	547	548	549	550	551	552	553	554	555	556	557	558	559	560	561	562	563	564	565	566	567	568	569	570	571	572	573	574	575	576	577	578	579	580	581	582	583	584	585	586	587	588	589	590	591	592	593	594	595	596	597	598	599	600	601	602	603	604	605	606	607	608	609	610	611	612	613	614	615	616	617	618	619	620	621	622	623	624	625	626	627	628	629	630	631	632	633	634	635	636	637	638	639	640	641	642	643	644	645	646	647	648	649	650	651	652	653	654	655	656	657	658	659	660	661	662	663	664	665	666	667	668	669	670	671	672	673	674	675	676	677	678	679	680	681	682	683	684	685	686	687	688	689	690	691	692	693	694	695	696	697	698	699	700	701	702	703	704	705	706	707	708	709	710	711	712	713	714	715	716	717	718	719	720	721	722	723	724	725	726	727	728	729	730	731	732	733	734	735	736	737	738	739	740	741	742	743	744	745	746	747	748	749	750	751	752	753	754	755	756	757	758	759	760	761	762	763	764	765	766	767	768	769	770	771	772	773	774	775	776	777	778	779	780	781	782	783	784	785	786	787	788	789	790	791	792	793	794	795	796	797	798	799	800	801	802	803	804	805	806	807	808	809	810	811	812	813	814	815	816	817	818	819	820	821	822	823	824	825	826	827	828	829	830	831	832	833	834	835	836	837	838	839	840	841	842	843	844	845	846	847	848	849	850	851	852	853	854	855	856	857	858	859	860	861	862	863	864	865	866	867	868	869	870	871	872	873	874	875	876	877	878	879	880	881	882	883	884	885	886	887	888	889	890	891	892	893	894	895	896	897	898	899	900	901	902	903	904	905	906	907	908	909	910	911	912	913	914	915	916	917	918	919	920	921	922	923	924	925	926	927	928	929	930	931	932	933	934	935	936	937	938	939	940	941	942	943	944	945	946	947	948	949	950	951	952	953	954	955	956	957	958	959	960	961	962	963	964	965	966	967	968	969	970	971	972	973	974	975	976	977	978	979	980	981	982	983	984	985	986	987	988	989	990	991	992	993	994	995	996	997	998	999	1000	1001	1002	1003	1004	1005	1006	1007	1008	1009	1010	1011	1012	1013	1014	1015	1016	1017	1018	1019	1020	1021	1022	1023	1024	1025	1026	1027	1028	1029	1030	1031	1032	1033	1034	1035	1036	1037	1038	1039	1040	1041	1042	1043	1044	1045	1046	1047	1048	1049	1050	1051	1052	1053	1054	1055	1056	1057	1058	1059	1060	1061	1062	1063	1064	1065	1066	1067	1068	1069	1070	1071	1072	1073	1074	1075	1076	1077	1078	1079	1080	1081	1082	1083	1084	1085	1086	1087	1088	1089	1090	1091	1092	1093	1094	1095	1096	1097	1098	1099	1100	1101	1102	1103	1104	1105	1106	1107	1108	1109	1110	1111	1112	1113	1114	1115	1116	1117	1118	1119	1120	1121	1122	1123	1124	1125	1126	1127	1128	1129	1130	1131	1132	1133	1134	1135	1136	1137	1138	1139	1140	1141	1142	1143	1144	1145	1146	1147	1148	1149	1150	1151	1152	1153	1154	1155	1156	1157	1158	1159	1160	1161	1162	1163	1164	1165	1166	1167	1168	1169	1170	1171	1172	1173	1174	1175	1176	1177	1178	1179	1180	1181	1182	1183	1184	1185	1186	1187	1188	1189	1190	1191	1192	1193	1194	1195	1196	1197	1198	1199	1200	1201	1202	1203	1204	1205	1206	1207	1208	1209	1210	1211	1212	1213	1214	1215	1216	1217	1218	1219	1220	1221	1222	1223	1224	1225	1226	1227	1228	1229	1230	1231	1232	1233	1234	1235	1236	1237	1238	1239	1240	1241	1242	1243	1244	1245	1246	1247	1248	1249	1250	1251	1252	1253	1254	1255	1256	1257	1258	1259	1260	1261	1262	1263	1264	1265	1266	1267	1268	1269	1270	1271	1272	1273	1274	1275	1276	1277	1278	1279	1280	1281	1282	1283	1284	1285	1286	1287	1288	1289	1290	1291	1292	1293	1294	1295	1296	1297	1298	1299	1300	1301	1302	1303	1304	1305	1306	1307	1308	1309	1310	1311	1312	1313	1314	1315	1316	1317	1318	1319	1320	1321	1322	1323	1324	1325	1326	1327	1328	1329	1330	1331	1332	1333	1334	1335	1336	1337	1338	1339	1340	1341	1342	1343	1344	1345	1346	1347	1348	1349	1350	1351	1352	1353	1354	1355	1356	1357	1358	1359	1360	1361	1362	1363	1364	1365	1366	1367	1368	1369	1370	1371	1372	1373	1374	1375	1376	1377	1378	1379	1380	1381	1382	1383	1384	1385	1386	1387	1388	1389	1390	1391	1392	1393	1394	1395	1396	1397	1398	1399	1400	1401	1402	1403	1404	1405	1406	1407	1408	1409	1410	1411	1412	1413	1414	1415	1416	1417	1418	1419	1420	1421	1422	1423	1424	1425	1426	1427	1428	1429	1430	1431	1432	1433	1434	1435	1436	1437	1438	1439	1440	1441	1442	1443	1444	1445	1446	1447	1448	1449	1450	1451	1452	1453	1454	1455	1456	1457	1458	1459	1460	1461	1462	1463	1464	1465	1466	1467	1468	1469	1470	1471	1472	1473	1474	1475

3. Results

3.1. State of conservation

Only one method of seed preservation is attested: carbonization. Through the action of fire, organic matter is replaced by carbon (Bakels 1984a, 1984b). Several factors influence the quality of charred remains, including temperature, duration of exposure to fire, oxygen supply, and humidity levels during contact with fire. Charred remains often shrink, crack under the heat, turn black, and lose surface ornamentation such as hairs or spines.

The predominance of carbonized remains in the corpus is unsurprising, as most archaeological sites yield primarily dry sediments, which predominantly preserve carbonized plant remains (Bakels 1984a, 1984b). Despite the destructive effects of carbonization, certain plant elements retain their overall shape and anatomical features, enabling precise identification—often at the genus level and sometimes at the species level (Bouby 2000). However, analyzing only these dry contexts is insufficient for a comprehensive understanding of a site (Wilson 1984). Carbonized remains are not entirely representative of the plant environment or the full range of human activities at a site (Bouby 2000). Instead, they often reflect anthropogenic actions, either deliberate or accidental. Plants subjected to fire during human use are more likely to be preserved through carbonization (Van der Venn 1985). Consequently, dry-environment sites often demonstrate an abundance of cereals and legumes, while other taxa, such as fruits, aromatics, and wild plants, are underrepresented or absent. This trend is evident in the current study, where fruit trees and wild plants are poorly represented in the charred contexts of Ulpiana.

Using the conservation scale for carbonized seeds published in 1990 by Boardman and Jones (1990), as well as Hubbard and Al Azm (1990), the state of preservation of carpological material at the site is assessed as average (Matterne 2001). This is not unusual, as dry contexts rarely yield optimally preserved seeds. Storage conditions for cereals, however, are relatively favorable, with only 29% of cereal seeds classified as *Cerealia indeterminata* (Figure 9). These seeds belong to cultivated Poaceae, indicating domesticated food plants, but their deteriorated surfaces, morphological deformations, and high fragmentation prevent precise identification.

Chaff remains are absent from the study, except for a single spikelet base. Combined with the low representation of cultivated field weeds, this suggests that the occupants of the studied areas were likely consumers rather than agricultural producers. None of the spaces studied can be definitively identified as areas for processing or storing agricultural products.

The analysis also revealed fragments of carbonized organic matter (MOC), which may represent residues of accidentally charred food preparations (e.g., bread, porridge, pancakes, or oatmeal) or fragments of cereals exposed to excessively high temperatures. Legumes exhibit relatively average preservation, with 27% classified under the term *Leguminosae sativae indeterminata* (Figure 10). Like cereals, these are cultivated Fabaceae, indicating domesticated food plants, but they cannot be identified at a more specific level. This high percentage of indeterminate legumes can be attributed to their

fragility during carbonization: the hilum, a key feature for species differentiation, is rarely preserved. The presence of carbonized seeds underscores the anthropogenic nature of the remains studied. As a result, the plant environment of the Ulpiana site is largely understood through the lens of human activity and its associated selections (Bouby 2000).

Figure 9: Percentage of caryopsis identified within the cereal corpus

Figure 10: Percentage of cotyledons identified within the legume corpus

3.2. Representativeness of the data

The density of seeds per liter of raw sediment varies between samples. Twelve samples were negative (7, 14, 18, 19, 21, 25, 26, 30, 34, 40, 41, and 50), while forty-five samples yielded a low density of macroremains, ranging from 1 to 10 seeds per liter of sediment (1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 16, 20, 22, 23, 24, 27, 28, 29, 31, 32, 33, 35, 36, 38, 39, 42, 43, 44, 45, 46, 47, 48, 49, 51, 52, 53, 54, 55, 56, 57, 58, 59, and 60). Three samples exhibited an average density of seeds, ranging from 10 to 100 seeds per liter (15, 17, and 37). Carpologists consider that low and medium concentration rates are sufficient to identify the plant species most frequently consumed or processed at a site. These concentrations thus provide insight into the dietary habits of the populations occupying the site during the chronological phases analyzed. In the present study, only the most commonly consumed plant species were identified.

3.3. Carpological data

3.3.1. Food(s) over the centuries

The carpological data for the 1st century AD are too sparse to support any hypotheses, as a single sample yielded only five seeds. The samples from the 2nd century AD all originate from the 1400/1400 sector. The carpological corpus is largely dominated by food taxa, particularly cereals and legumes. Cereals are represented by three species. Spelt wheat (*Triticum spelta*) is a winter grain (Jacomet and Karg 1996) with minimal growing requirements (Matterne 2001). It is a hulled wheat that yields better than emmer (*Triticum dicoccon*) (Sigaut 1989), and its flour is suitable for making bread (Matterne 2001). Notably, spelt wheat serves as an effective compromise to naked wheat (Matterne 2001). Although spelt appeared to be a secondary grain throughout the protohistoric period, its cultivation increased significantly during the Roman conquest.

Free-threshing wheats (*Triticum aestivum/durum/turgidum*) were also consumed. These wheats require favorable climatic conditions (neither too humid nor too dry) and richer soils than spelt and polystic barley (Matterne 2001). While more delicate to cultivate, naked wheat offers advantages such as a higher gluten content, enabling the production of yeast breads, compared to barley or hulled wheat (Matterne 2001).

Finally, barley (*Hordeum vulgare subsp. vulgare*) is present. Unlike hulled wheat, barley is a summer cereal with lower nutrient requirements and the ability to thrive in a broader range of climatic conditions.

Chaff remains are absent from this period; only the caryopses are observed. Fragments of carbonized organic matter (MOC) are also attested.

Various legumes were consumed in Ulpiana during the 2nd century AD. These include pea (*Pisum sativum*) and vetch (*Vicia sp.*), which are commonly found in Roman archaeological contexts (Matterne 2001). Of particular interest is the occurrence of bitter vetch (*Vicia ervilia*). This plant, with its earliest attestations in Syria, likely spread to Europe via the Danube (Mikic 2016). Although bitter vetch played a significant role in the diet of European populations for millennia (Bouby 2000), its consumption declined

significantly during Roman times (Matterne 2014; Pradat 2013). However, in Ulpiana, bitter vetch is the most represented legume during the 2nd and 3rd centuries. This trend may be specific to the continental Balkans during the Roman era, as other sites, such as Čurug - Stari Vinogradi and Hrtkovci – Vran in Serbia (Medovic and Mikic 2014), Caričin Grad in Serbia (Birk et al. 2014), and Virovitica in Croatia (Šoštarić et al. 2014), also demonstrate the presence of bitter vetch in Roman contexts.

At Caričin Grad, archaeobotanists suggest that bitter vetch may have been used as a forage plant due to its toxicity (Birk et al. 2014). However, it should be noted that repeated cooking can render bitter vetch digestible. In Ulpiana, bitter vetch was found carbonized alongside cereals and legumes. Combined with the low representation of agricultural weeds, this suggests that its consumption at the site was entirely plausible. Overall, Ulpiana clearly aligns with the regional trend of bitter vetch persistence during the Roman era. Current evidence suggests that this trend is confined to the continental Balkans.

No fruit, aromatic, or oilseed species have been identified in contexts from the 2nd century AD. The transition between the 2nd and 3rd centuries AD marks the appearance of new taxa. The observed increase in dietary diversity during this phase may, however, be influenced by a methodological bias, as larger volumes of raw sediment and a greater number of samples were analyzed compared to the previous phase.

Wheat continues to dominate the cereal corpus, but naked wheat is now better represented than hulled wheat. Rye (*Secale cereale*) appears and, after wheat, becomes the most represented cereal taxon, while barley is underrepresented.

Legumes show increased diversity as well. Bitter vetch remains dominant, but broad bean (*Vicia faba*) is added to the previously identified pea (*Pisum sativum*) and vetch (*Vicia sp.*). Fruit trees are also attested during this phase: grapes (*Vitis vinifera subsp. vinifera*), peaches (*Prunus persica*), and hazelnuts (*Corylus avellana*) were cultivated or gathered before being consumed.

During the 3rd and 4th centuries AD, wheat and barley remain present, but millet (*Panicum miliaceum*) makes its first appearance. Millet is a summer cereal with a relatively short growing season, allowing it to be sown in spring if winter cereals fail. Post-harvest processing requires shelling and crushing. It is not well-suited for breadmaking and was primarily consumed as porridge or in stews (Jedrusiak and Wiethold 2021). Typically, millet is stored in its hulled form, with the palea and lemma providing a protective covering (Lundström-Baudais and Bailly 1995; Lundström et al. 2002). Once hulled, millet spoils quickly (Sigaut 1988; Bouby 2003).

Among legumes, bitter vetch is no longer attested in this phase, while lentils (*Lens culinaris*) make their first appearance. Additionally, a fragment of prunus (*Prunus spp.*) and elderberry seeds (*Sambucus sp.*) indicate fruit consumption during this period. The diet during the 4th and 5th centuries AD remains largely consistent, featuring naked wheat, hulled wheat, barley, millet, peas, and vetch. Grass pea (*Lathyrus sativus*) appears for the first time. However, it remains unclear whether this represents an actual diversification of plant foods or a result of methodological bias.

Grapes continue to be consumed, and there are first occurrences of walnut (*Juglans regia*) and raspberry (*Rubus idaeus*).

The final phase studied, spanning the 5th and 6th centuries AD, shows a decline in the

diversity of food taxa. However, this decrease is likely attributable to methodological bias, as the number of samples analyzed during this period was lower than in earlier phases.

3.3.2. Agricultural practices and livelihoods

The diet of the Ulpiana population consisted of locally grown plant species, including various cereals, legumes, and certain fruit trees. This was supplemented by the practice of gathering, as taxa such as elderberry, walnut, and hazel produced fruits that were foraged. Thus, the inhabitants of Ulpiana had access to multiple sources of plant-based foods.

No imported food taxa have been identified, suggesting that, based on current evidence, all plant foods were produced locally in Ulpiana. The presence of both winter and summer cereals, along with their associated agricultural weeds (in very limited quantities), further indicates a strong mastery of agricultural practices, particularly the principle of crop rotation. However, this does not necessarily imply that the occupants of the studied sectors were agricultural producers. On the contrary, no evidence of harvest processing has been detected.

Although taxa such as *Chenopodietea* (annual vegetation of crops and anthropized areas) and *Secalietea* (weed species associated with winter crops) are present, they are found in very small quantities. Additionally, the absence of storage structures and chaff remains strongly suggests that the temple and basilica areas served purposes other than agricultural or food production. Instead, it is likely that the inhabitants of this sector were simply consumers.

3.3.3. The Roman presence in Dardania and taxonomic evolution

The carpological data for Kosova remain too limited to establish a definitive assessment on this topic. However, a comparison between the data presented here and the carpological analysis conducted in 2018 at the Cërnice site (excavated by Premtim Alaj and Sedat Baraliu during 2018) (see Figure 10) helps to clarify certain aspects. This Iron Age site yielded 5,642 seeds from a single post hole, all of which were dehusked caryopses. Unlike Ulpiana, the analysis of Cërnice reveals the predominance of hulled wheat, particularly emmer (*Triticum dicoccon*), with 2,632 seeds identified. Einkorn (*Triticum monococcum*) is also present but in significantly smaller quantities, with 119 seeds attested.

A few centuries later, the dominance of hulled wheats, which were essential at Cërnice, had either disappeared or become a minority at Ulpiana, where carpological assemblages are dominated by naked wheats. This shift is not unique to Dardania or the Balkans; it is a pattern observed across all regions under Roman influence throughout the Empire. While naked wheat is more sensitive to climatic conditions, the Roman period experienced a minor climatic optimum, which supported good yields. The simpler post-harvest processing requirements and the bread-making advantages of naked wheat likely explain its widespread adoption across the Roman Empire, which

has often been referred to as the “bread civilization.”

Cërnicë (Kosovo) RO: Premtim Alaj et Baraliu Sadat	Sample number				code phyto- sociologique (d'après Ellenberg et al. 1991)
	Structure	Post hole		Total volume (l)	
	Volume (l)	1		1	
	Density/l	5642			
	Datating	Iron Age			
Scientific names	Vernacular names	Type of reste	Method of conservation	Number of restes	
Lambinon et alii (2012)	Lambinon et alii (2012)				
Cereal					
<i>Triticum dicoccon</i>	Emmer	caryopsis	C	2632	x
<i>Hordeum vulgare</i> subsp. <i>vulgare</i>	Barley	caryopsis	C	168	x
<i>Triticum monococcum</i>	Einkorn wheat	caryopsis	C	119	x
<i>Triticum</i> sp.	Wheat	caryopsis	C	2628	x
<i>Hordeum</i> sp.	Barley	caryopsis	C	1	x
Cerealia	Cereal	caryopsis	C	90	x
Legume					
<i>Vicia sativa</i> agg.	Common Vetch	seed	C	1	x
Leguminosae sativae indeterminata	Indeterminate legumes	seed	C	1	x
Other					
<i>Avena/Bromus</i> sp.	Brome/Avoine	caryopsis	C	2	x
Number of restes				5 642	
Nombre of taxa				9	
Main conservation within the structure				C	

Figure 11: Carpological study of Cërnicë (Kosova)

Conclusion

The carpological data collected at Ulpiana during the last five excavation campaigns are crucial for understanding the history of the Roman continental Balkans. This analysis contributes to the limited studies conducted in the region and highlights the striking similarity between the carpological assemblages of Ulpiana and Justiniana Prima, located nearby. Both sites show an absence of plant imports. However, further studies are required to determine whether this observation represents a definitive trend. The persistence of bitter vetch (*Vicia ervilia*) during the Roman era stands out as a unique characteristic of the region, confirmed by other carpological analyses conducted across the Balkans.

Beyond this, the carpological assemblages of Ulpiana are currently comparable to those found at Roman sites in the northern Mediterranean. These assemblages are dominated by naked wheat and barley, along with some legumes and fruit trees, which were primarily cultivated or foraged.

It is important to emphasize that these findings represent only the initial carpological data from Ulpiana. Further analysis in the coming years is essential, as a Roman settlement situated between the Adriatic and the Danube undoubtedly holds great potential for uncovering new archaeological insights.

Conflict of Interest

There are no conflicts of interest to declare regarding this publication.

ENDNOTES

1 For a full view of the research at Ulpiana, see the site report “Ulpiana / Iustiniana secunda (Kosovo), 2023” by Christophe Goddard, Arben Hajdari, Milot Berisha [<https://www.archeo.ens.fr/Ulpiana-Iustiniana-secunda-Kosovo.html?lang=fr>, accessed last 30 June 2024]

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